

TREAT-MMTB: Transformative Research and Efficient Ai Technologies for Multimodal Management of Tuberculosis 2025: Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

TREAT-MMTB: Transformative Research and Efficient Ai Technologies for Multimodal Management of Tuberculosis 2025

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

TREAT-MMTB 2025

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Pulmonary tuberculosis (TB) remains one of the most critical global health challenges, affecting millions of individuals annually and imposing substantial morbidity and mortality. Chest X-ray (CXR) examination is an essential tool for TB screening, triage, and diagnosis. Accurate disease diagnosis and identification of TB lesions on CXRs, such as consolidation and cavity, are crucial for optimizing treatment, monitoring patient outcomes, and allocating resources efficiently, particularly in resource-constrained settings . Radiological features, such as cavity presence and lung area involvement, are established indicators of TB severity(Nachiappan et al., 2017). However, manual interpretation of chest X-rays is time-intensive and dependent on radiologist expertise, which may not always be available.

This challenge addresses these gaps by introducing two innovative tasks. Task 1 focuses on cavity presence detection and segmentation, using advanced deep learning techniques to identify and quantify cavities in CXRs. Task 2 expands the scope to a multimodal approach for TB diagnosis, combining radiological data with clinical information to develop robust, explainable, and generalizable AI models.

From a biomedical perspective, the challenge aims to enhance diagnostic accuracy and improve disease monitoring by providing consistent and reproducible assessments. Technically, it leverages state-of-the-art machine learning models to develop automated, explainable, and scalable tools suitable for diverse healthcare environments. The anticipated impact includes facilitating personalized treatment planning, reducing dependency on radiological expertise, and addressing disparities in TB care globally.

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

Pulmonary tuberculosis, Chest X-ray, Large multi-modal model, Multi-modality dataset, Cavity segmentation, TB diagnosis, Resource-limited healthcare

Year

2025

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

While many AI-driven tools exist for tuberculosis (TB) detection, this challenge uniquely focuses on enhancing diagnostic accuracy using multimodal inputs. The specific novel aspects include:

1. Cavity presence detection and segmentation: Cavity is a clinically crucial factor for treatment outcomes and contact investigation, yet it has not been thoroughly explored in previous research. This task emphasizes the development of accurate cavity detection and segmentation models, addressing a significant gap in the field.
2. Integration of multimodal diagnostic features: The challenge combines radiological data with clinical and demographic information to improve diagnostic robustness, enabling the deep learning model to be more transparent and explainable which is close to human-level clinical decision making . This approach moves beyond conventional reliance on CXR images alone, integrating a more comprehensive view of patient data to identify TB cases more effectively.
3. Data diversity for robust model development: The challenge provides a diverse dataset that includes publicly available TB Portals data from around the world as well as private datasets from Korea, Mongolia, and Peru. This ensures the development of models with enhanced robustness and generalizability.

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

[Task 1] Cavity presence detection and segmentation

This task focuses on developing algorithms for automatically determining the presence or absence of lung cavities on chest X-rays (CXRs) and segmenting them when present. Accurate detection and segmentation of cavities are critical for assessing disease extent in pulmonary tuberculosis (TB). Cavities are a significant clinical indicator of TB severity and correlate strongly with bacterial load and infectiousness (Kim et al., 2021). By combining cavity presence detection with precise segmentation, this task enables robust and quantitative assessments of affected lung areas, aiding both diagnosis and monitoring treatment outcomes. This dual approach is particularly beneficial in resource-limited settings, where radiologist expertise may not always be available. The task leverages advanced deep learning techniques to identify and delineate cavities with high accuracy and consistency. This facilitates standardized assessments crucial for clinical decision-making and contributes to scalable AI solutions that enhance TB care globally.

[Task 2] Multimodal TB diagnosis

This task focuses on diagnosing TB using a combination of clinical data and radiological features, leveraging multimodal deep learning frameworks. The integration of clinical data (e.g., symptoms, bacterial load, demographic information) with imaging features derived from chest X-rays (e.g., lung abnormalities, cavity presence, and consolidation patterns) aims to enhance diagnostic accuracy. Advanced natural language processing techniques will analyze clinical notes and reports, while imaging models will identify TB-specific

radiographic patterns.

By transitioning from unimodal (e.g., CXRs alone) to multimodal approaches, this task seeks to create AI models capable of providing reliable and comprehensive TB diagnosis across diverse populations and healthcare environments. These models will enable faster, more accurate TB detection, facilitating timely treatment and improved disease management, particularly in resource-constrained settings.

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

N/A

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

Half day

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

TB remains a significant clinical and epidemiological challenge globally, making it essential to emphasize its clinical importance through expert-led presentations and collaborative discussions. The event will be conducted in a single session, either in the morning or afternoon. This session will include expert lectures on TB's clinical aspects, hosted by organizing institutions like the Light Foundation and NIAID, followed by prize distribution, model presentations, and a panel discussion to foster mutual learning and growth among participants.

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

Estimate: 100 teams.

Basis: TB remains one of the most pressing medical challenges for humanity, attracting global attention and requiring immediate action. Additionally, the growing interest in multimodal tasks is expected to drive substantial participation as this approach includes elements that explain the automatic decision-making process.

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

Yes, we plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

1. Training and internal validation: Training will be conducted using participants' personal computing resources. Participants will download the provided datasets, develop their models, and upload their final models for internal validation to compare its model against each other.

External validation: External validation will be performed on a dedicated platform, such as Kaggle.com, to ensure

consistent and fair assessments including private datasets from South Korea,, and Peru.

On-site: Projectors, computers, and microphones for presentations and discussions.

TASK 1: Cavity presence detection and segmentation

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

A cavity on CXRs is a hallmark of TB severity, closely linked to bacterial load, transmission risk, and treatment outcomes. Task 1 focuses on developing automated approaches for cavity presence detection and segmentation, addressing the limitations of manual radiological assessments. Using advanced deep learning techniques, this task aims to first determine the presence or absence of cavities on CXRs and, if present, detect and delineate their boundaries with high accuracy and precision. By enabling both the detection and segmentation of cavities, this task facilitates standardized and reproducible evaluations crucial for clinical decision-making. From a biomedical perspective, automating cavity detection and segmentation empowers clinicians with reliable tools to assess disease burden and monitor therapeutic responses. Technically, this task drives innovations in medical image analysis by integrating classification and segmentation methodologies, contributing to scalable and generalizable AI solutions for global health applications. The anticipated impact includes enhancing the consistency of TB severity grading, streamlining patient management in resource-limited settings, and improving the understanding of cavity-driven disease progression.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Pulmonary tuberculosis, Chest X-ray, Radiology, Cavity detection, Cavity segmentation, vision

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

1. Namguk Kim, PhD - University of Ulsan College of Medicine, Republic of Korea
2. Soon Ho Yoon, MD, PhD - Seoul National University Hospital, Republic of Korea
3. Bold Bayarbaatar, MD, MSc - Intermed Hospital, Ulaanbaatar, Mongolia
4. Boiter, Eric, MS - National Institutes of Health / National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Diseases, USA
5. Hyun-Jin Bae, Ph.D - Promedius inc.
6. Sei Won Lee, MD, PhD - Asan Medical Center, Republic of Korea
7. Young Ae Kang, MD, PhD - Severance Hospital, Republic of Korea
8. The Korean Society of Thoracic Radiology

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Soon Ho Yoon, MD, PhD - Seoul National University Hospital, Republic of Korea

Email: yshoka@gmail.com

Phone: 82-10-4029-0279

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI 2025

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

<https://www.kaggle.com/>

or other platform (<https://grand-challenge.org/>, Naver T2 cloud, etc)

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

<https://www.kaggle.com/competitions/TREAT-MMTB> (we will create it if this proposal is accepted)

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

Publicly available data is allowed

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

The first, second, and third team will receive awards. The awards stipend is to be determined.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

Top three performing methods will be announced publicly on the challenge website. The participants will be invited to present their method during an oral presentation. These teams will be listed as co-authors in the final manuscript.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

Contributors to the submissions covered in the manuscript will be invited to serve as co-authors of the TREAT-MMTB Journal article.

This will include, at a minimum, the top-performing teams selected to present their methodologies at the workshop. Additionally, submissions that exhibit notable scientific value may also be included as co-authors in the journal publication.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

- Participants must submit their models as Docker containers, adhering to the requirements outlined by the Kaggle platform. Each team is permitted to submit one model per task type, such as segmentation or multimodal analysis. The Docker container should encompass all necessary components for execution, including preprocessing, inference, and postprocessing.

- While fine-tuning or training the entire model on the platform will not be permitted, participants are encouraged to leverage pretrained models and ensure the containerized submissions are capable of performing the intended tasks without user interaction. Resource limitations such as computational time and hardware requirements will be predefined to ensure computational feasibility and fairness. These constraints will be clearly communicated prior to the challenge.

- The detailed instructions for container preparation and submission will be provided on the official TREAT-MMTB challenge page hosted on the Kaggle platform. Additionally, participants are required to make the code for their postprocessing steps publicly available after the challenge to foster transparency and reproducibility.

- Evaluation will be performed on a sequestered test set, with only one submission allowed per team during the final phase. The evaluation platform will execute the Docker containers in a fully automated manner, and results will be reported back to participants through the platform interface.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

1. Internal Validation:

Participants will have access to an internal validation set to evaluate the performance of their models. The ground truth for this validation set will not be provided. Teams will be allowed to submit their Docker containers to the

challenge platform once per week during this phase. The evaluation will be executed automatically, and the results will be displayed on a live leaderboard to help teams track their progress. This phase is designed to enable participants to fine-tune their models and ensure proper functionality without compromising the integrity of the ground truth data.

2. External Testing:

Once the final submission deadline has passed, participants' last submitted models will be evaluated on a sequestered external test set.

The external test set results will serve as the sole basis for final rankings, and no additional submissions will be permitted after the final phase begins.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

15 April 2025: Registration opens

Participants will be able to register for the challenge in the Kaggle, from the date of its potential acceptance (April 15, 2025) until the (July 31, 2025).

15 April 2025: Training and validation data release

Availability of training data (with ground truth labels) and validation data (without ground truth labels).

15 August 2025: Docker submission deadline.

Evaluation on testing data by the organizers, only for participants with submitted short papers. Submissions will be scored based on the evaluation metrics, and rankings will be determined accordingly.

22 August 2025: Invitation to participate

Inviting all participants with valid submissions (paper + docker) to present at the conference (type of presentation will be determined within the next 2 weeks)

1 September 2025: Release of Challenge Results

Final challenge results will be announced.

Contacting top-performing teams for preparing oral presentations.

23 September 2025: Challenge at MICCAI

Oral presentation of final top 3 ranked teams and awards ceremony

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

This is being done under a TB portal data use agreement (DUA) with NIAID.

DUA: <https://tbportals.niaid.nih.gov/pdf/TB-Portals-Data-Use-Agreement.pdf>

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

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Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

We will provide the evaluation code to challenge participants alongside the final batch of the training data. This release is planned for mid-July.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Participants are required to encapsulate their inference algorithms and associated model weights into a Docker container. The challenge organizers will ensure that the participants' source code and model weights remain confidential and will not be disclosed publicly during the evaluation phase. After the challenge is finished, code and model weights from selected participating teams with leading scores will be made publicly available.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

The TREAT-MMTB challenge is supported by the National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Diseases (NIAID), USA and RIGHT foundation, korea.

Financial support from Promedius inc., etc.

Financial support from The Korean Society of Thoracic Radiology

The industrial sponsors of the challenge will not have access to the test data for the duration of the challenge but may access the data once the full dataset is released to the public upon completion of the challenge.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

CAD,Treatment planning

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Detection,Segmentation

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target cohort for this challenge comprises patients presenting with symptoms suggestive of pulmonary tuberculosis (TB) who visit outpatient clinics for evaluation. These patients are characterized by the availability of clinical data collected during routine diagnostic workups, including frontal chest X-rays (CXRs), sputum sample results (if indicated), and demographic information. CXRs are used to assess radiological features indicative of TB, employing validated scoring systems such as the Timika score. Sputum samples, when obtained, provide information about bacterial burden through microscopy or culture tests. The cohort reflects the population commonly encountered in initial diagnostic settings, ensuring the AI model's applicability in real-world clinical workflows to inform subsequent diagnostic and treatment strategies.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge cohort includes datasets curated for training, validation, and testing of AI models focused on pulmonary tuberculosis (TB). The training and validation datasets are derived from the publicly available National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Diseases (NIAID) TB portal, which compiles data from 13 countries, including annotated chest X-rays (CXRs) and associated metadata such as bacterial burden and cavitation status. For testing, independent datasets from hospitals in Korea, Mongolia, and Peru are utilized. These datasets consist of locally annotated CXRs and matched clinical and sputum data, reflecting diverse geographic and clinical contexts. This approach ensures that the challenge cohort represents real-world diagnostic scenarios, enabling robust evaluation of AI model performance across different populations and healthcare settings.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Chest x-ray - poasteroanterior(PA) view

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

Segmentation mask of cavity

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

Epidemiology: age, gender

Clinical information: diagnosis code, bmi

Sputum: Culture, Drug-resistance

Treatment: regimen, duration, outcome

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

thorax shown in chest x-ray data

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

lung in the thorax

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy,Robustness

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

The data was acquired from over 16 countries worldwide, ensuring a diverse representation of clinical settings. Consequently, a variety of imaging devices from multiple manufacturers were used, including but not limited to GE Healthcare, Canon Inc., Fujifilm Holdings Corporation, Siemens AG, and Philips Healthcare.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

Each center utilized its own imaging protocols and equipment configurations, leading to variations in device settings and performance. This diversity enhances the robustness of the dataset by encompassing a wide range of imaging quality and characteristics.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Scientific Research Institute of Lung Diseases, Ministry of Health, Baku (Azerbaijan)

The United Institute of Informatics Problems, National Academy of Sciences of Belarus, Minsk (Belarus)

Republican Research and Practical Centre for Pulmonology and Tuberculosis, Minsk (Belarus)

Shenzhen Center for Chronic Disease Control, Shenzhen (China)

Fondation Congolaise pour la Recherche Medicale (Republic of the Congo)

National Center for Tuberculosis and Lung Diseases, Ministry of Health, Tbilisi (Georgia)

Manipal Academy of Higher Education, Karnataka (India)

National Science Center of Phthisiopulmonology, Almaty (Kazakhstan)

National Tuberculosis Center, Bishkek (Kyrgyzstan)

University Clinical Research Center, Bamako (Mali)

Universidad Autónoma de Nuevo León, Monterrey (Mexico)

Phthisiopneumology Institute, Chisinau (Moldova)

University of Ibadan, Ibadan (Nigeria)

Marius Nasta Pneumophtisiology Institute, Bucuresti (Romania)

Hospital Center University De Fann, Senegal (Senegal)

Perinatal HIV Research Unit, Johannesburg (South Africa)

Kharkiv National Medical University, Kharkiv (Ukraine)

National Lung Hospital, Hanoi (Vietnam)

Asan Medical Center, Seoul (Republic of Korea)

Seoul National University Hospital, Seoul (Republic of Korea)

Severance Hospital, Seoul (Republic of Korea)

Hospital Nacional Dos de Mayo, (Republic of Peru)

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

The diagnosis and treatment decisions for TB patients involved respiratory physicians and other clinical specialists. The labeling of chest X-rays was carried out by radiologists as well as trained general practitioners (GPs) who received specific training for this task. This collaborative approach ensured that the dataset reflects a variety of expertise levels in clinical and radiological assessments.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

Both training and test cases will consist of chest X-ray (CXR) images from TB patients. The training set will primarily include weak labels indicating the presence or absence of cavities, with approximately 200 cases featuring strong labels in the form of cavity segmentation masks, performed by radiologists, for instances with cavities. Test cases will be accompanied by strong annotations provided through detailed cavity segmentation performed by radiologists. This structured approach ensures the model is trained on general patterns while leveraging high-quality annotations for rigorous evaluation.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

1. Public data for training and tuning: 400 cases from TB portal

2. Internal validation data: 100 cases from TB portal

3. External validation data: total 250 cases

50 cases from Asan Medical Center, Seoul (Republic of Korea)

50 cases from Seoul National University Hospital, Seoul (Republic of Korea)

- 50 cases from Severance Hospital, Seoul (Republic of Korea)
- 50 cases from Intermed Hospital, Ulaanbaatar (Mongolia)
- 50 cases from Hospital Nacional Dos de Mayo, (Republic of Peru)

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The selection of specific proportions for training, validation, and test cases in the tuberculosis (TB) challenge was carefully designed to ensure robustness and fairness in model evaluation.

For the training and validation datasets, the numbers were determined based on the total number of available cases in the public datasets, such as TB Portals. These datasets provide high-quality annotations and metadata, which are essential for developing reliable models. The selection was made by appropriately determining the number of cases based on the presence of cavities. To promote inclusivity and transparency, all available data were shared with participants, ensuring equal access to resources for model development. Additionally, a 20% subset of the public data was reserved for validation purposes. This separation allows for unbiased assessment of model performance since the validation data is not directly involved in the training process.

The test dataset was curated to include cases from multiple countries and institutions, ensuring the evaluation of models on diverse clinical practices and patient populations. This approach tests the generalizability of the models and their ability to handle domain shifts—a critical factor for real-world applications. The test data reflects the clinical proportions observed in real-world settings at each participating institution, with a total of 50 cases per institution. This sample size is sufficient to achieve statistical significance during evaluation while closely mirroring clinical conditions.

Overall, this design ensures that model performance is rigorously and fairly assessed, reflecting both the diversity and the practical realities of clinical deployment.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

The training, validation, and test cases will reflect the real-world distribution of TB patients in clinical settings at each participating institution. By maintaining the natural class distribution observed in these settings, the challenge aims to evaluate how well the models perform across diverse clinical environments. This approach is aligned with the primary goal of the challenge: to develop AI solutions that can effectively support treatment decisions in varied real-world scenarios. Testing models under these conditions ensures their practical utility and generalizability in helping clinicians across different clinical contexts.

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

Currently, no publicly available datasets include segmentation masks for cavities in TB patients. For this challenge, we plan to provide radiologist-generated ground truth segmentation masks for the test set images from each participating institution. This approach ensures that the test data includes high-quality annotations, enabling accurate evaluation of model performance.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

The training and validation datasets will be sourced from public data available in the TB Portal. These datasets already include annotations for cavity size prediction performed by radiologists and general practitioners (GPs) following established guidelines. This ensures that the annotations provided for training and validation are standardized and consistent with clinical practices.

For the 200 cases featuring strong labels, reference annotations for cavity size prediction will be created through human annotation. An experienced thoracic radiologist with 18 years of expertise (S.H.Y.) will develop the initial reference guidelines. Subsequently, two radiologists from each participating center will annotate the training and validation strong labels, as well as the labels for the test set, based on these guidelines. They will collaboratively review the annotations to ensure accuracy and consistency across all datasets.

Two radiologists from each center will complete the labeling by mid-March, and the annotations will be reviewed before the start of the challenge.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

For the test set, the included patients have both chest X-rays (CXR) and CT scans available. Annotators are instructed to first review the CT scans, which provide higher sensitivity, to confirm the presence and location of cavities. Using this information, they then identify the corresponding cavity lesions on the CXR at the same locations. Annotations involve segmenting the cavity wall on the CXR and extracting the maximum diameter of each identified cavity. This process ensures that the cavity segmentation on the CXR is both accurate and informed by the detailed insights from the CT scans. Detailed annotation protocols and training materials will be provided to the annotators to ensure consistency and reliability.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The training and validation annotations were performed by radiologists and general practitioners (GPs) under the guidelines provided by the TB Portal. For the test set, annotations will be conducted by two radiologists at each center, following a reference developed by an experienced thoracic radiologist with 18 years of expertise (S.H.Y.).

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

N/A

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The training and validation datasets provided through the NIAID TB portal will include DICOM header information, which will be openly accessible to participants. To ensure standardization, chest X-ray images from multiple hospitals will be preprocessed to conform to a consistent format.

Regarding radiology reports, variations in language and structure exist across different hospitals. To address this, reports will be provided in two clearly defined sections: Findings and Conclusions. However, no additional structured preprocessing will be performed beyond this classification. All reports will be preprocessed into

English before being shared with participants.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

1. Inter-annotator Variability: Differences in expertise and interpretation among annotators (e.g., radiologists and GPs for training and validation, or the two radiologists per center for the test set) could lead to inconsistencies in identifying and segmenting cavities. While collaborative reviews for consensus mitigate this, minor variations in segmentation boundaries may still occur.

2. Intra-annotator Variability: Even experienced annotators may show slight inconsistencies in repeated annotations, especially when identifying subtle features like cavity walls on CXRs.

3. CT-to-CXR Mapping: For test cases, the process of identifying cavities on CXRs based on CT scan references might introduce errors, particularly in accurately correlating features across modalities.

4. Segmentation Challenges: Variability may arise in delineating the cavity walls due to the inherent limitations of CXR resolution and image quality, which could affect the accuracy of segmentation and measurements like maximum diameter.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

1. Image Quality Variability: Differences in the quality of the chest X-rays (e.g., resolution, exposure levels, or artifacts) could impact the clarity of cavity features, leading to inconsistent interpretations or annotations.

2. Equipment and Acquisition Differences: Variability in imaging equipment and protocols across institutions could result in differences in image characteristics, such as contrast or sharpness, potentially influencing annotation accuracy.

3. Domain Shift Between Training and Test Data: The training and validation data from the TB Portal may have different characteristics compared to the test data sourced from various institutions, which could affect the generalizability of models trained on these datasets.

4. Clinical Context Limitations: Annotators relying solely on imaging data without access to the full clinical context (e.g., patient symptoms or laboratory findings) may misinterpret certain features, such as distinguishing between cavities and other abnormalities like consolidation.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

Multimetric evaluation

-Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)

-Accuracy

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

The evaluation metrics for the cavity presence detection and segmentation task will be reported separately as Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC) and Accuracy, rather than using a combined formula. This approach allows a more transparent evaluation of each model's ability to detect cavities and accurately segment their boundaries. The DSC was chosen for its suitability in biomedical image segmentation tasks, where precise delineation of pathological features, such as cavities in TB, is crucial. DSC measures the overlap between predicted segmentation and ground truth, providing a clear, interpretable assessment of accuracy. It is sensitive to both false positives and false negatives, ensuring a balanced evaluation. In the context of cavity prediction, accurate boundary identification is critical for clinical decisions, such as assessing disease severity or planning interventions. The DSC's ability to handle variations in cavity size and shape makes it highly relevant. Additionally, Accuracy is included as part of the evaluation due to the presence of TB cases without cavities. Accuracy is defined as the proportion of correct predictions (both true positives and true negatives) out of all predictions made. It combines the model's ability to correctly identify both TB with cavities and TB without cavities, ensuring that the model's performance is evaluated holistically, beyond just the cavity presence. By including accuracy, the metric accounts for the balance between correctly identifying non-cavity TB cases and minimizing false positives in cases with cavities.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

The performance ranking for Task 1 will be determined through a stepwise approach that separately evaluates Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC) and Accuracy before combining them to derive the final ranking.

First, all submitted algorithms will be independently ranked based on their DSC and Accuracy scores. The algorithm with the highest DSC score will receive rank 1 for DSC, and similarly, the algorithm with the highest Accuracy score will receive rank 1 for Accuracy. This ensures that segmentation performance and classification performance are evaluated on their own merits.

Next, to determine the final ranking, the DSC rank and Accuracy rank for each algorithm will be summed together. The lower the total rank sum, the better the overall performance of the algorithm. For example, if an algorithm ranks 1st in DSC and 1st in Accuracy, its final score will be 2. If another algorithm ranks 2nd in DSC and 3rd in Accuracy, its final score will be 5.

In the case of ties, where multiple algorithms have the same final score, a secondary criterion will be used. The algorithm with the higher sum of its DSC and Accuracy values will be ranked higher. This ensures that if two teams have the same rank sum, the one with the overall better actual performance across both metrics is prioritized. If the tie persists even after this step, an additional tiebreaker will prioritize the algorithm with the higher DSC score, as precise segmentation is particularly crucial for clinical applications.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

If a submission fails to produce a segmentation result for a specific test case, the Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC) for that case will be set to 0. Additionally, if the accuracy for detecting cavity presence is missing, it will also be set to 0.

This ensures that missing results negatively impact the final mean score, discouraging incomplete submissions while maintaining fairness in the evaluation.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

The chosen ranking scheme ensures a fair and balanced evaluation by independently ranking DSC and Accuracy before combining them. This approach recognizes different strengths in segmentation and classification, preventing bias toward a specific metric.

By summing the individual ranks, models that perform well across both metrics are prioritized. In case of ties, the algorithm with the higher sum of DSC and Accuracy values is ranked higher, ensuring that overall performance is considered. If ties persist, DSC is used as the final tiebreaker, given its critical role in clinical decision-making.

This method encourages well-rounded model development, maintains clinical relevance, and ensures fairness in ranking.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

Statistical significance will be evaluated by analyzing between-class variability across selected subsets, such as case difficulty and participant demographics. This approach will provide insights into how robust the methods are under varying conditions. Python will be used to conduct all statistical analyses, including ranking calculations and variability assessments.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

The described statistical methods were chosen to provide a robust and fair evaluation of the submitted algorithms. By assessing between-class variability across subsets such as case difficulty and demographics, we aim to ensure that the models perform consistently across different scenarios. This approach also accounts for potential domain shifts, reflecting real-world variations.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

1. **Combining Algorithms via Ensembling:** After individual evaluations, ensemble methods (e.g., averaging predictions or majority voting) may be explored to assess whether combining multiple submissions improves performance.

2. **Inter-Algorithm Variability:** Variability in performance across algorithms will be analyzed by comparing their scores on specific subsets of test cases (e.g., cases with mild, moderate, or severe TB). This analysis will identify strengths and weaknesses of different methods and highlight scenarios where certain algorithms excel or

struggle.

3. Common Problems/Biases of Submitted Methods: A review of errors across submissions will be conducted to identify common biases, such as systematic under-segmentation in cavity detection or misclassification of severe TB cases. These insights could guide future algorithm development and highlight areas where additional data or refinement is needed.

TASK 2: Multimodal TB Diagnosis

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Accurate diagnosis of pulmonary TB is critical for timely treatment and effective disease management, particularly in diverse and resource-constrained healthcare environments. Task 2 focuses on multimodal TB diagnosis by integrating radiological findings from CXRs with clinical and demographic data. This task aims to develop robust, interpretable AI models capable of identifying TB cases with high accuracy by leveraging features such as lung abnormalities, cavitation presence, and consolidation patterns. By combining multiple data modalities, the models promise to surpass traditional diagnostic approaches that rely solely on radiological interpretation. Biomedically, this task enhances diagnostic precision and supports the early identification of TB, especially in patients with atypical presentations or comorbidities. Technically, it advances multimodal AI by addressing challenges related to data fusion, generalizability, and explainability in medical applications. The anticipated outcomes include fostering equitable TB care, enabling faster and more reliable diagnosis, and contributing to the global efforts against TB through scalable, data-driven innovations.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

Pulmonary tuberculosis, Chest X-ray, Diagnosis, Radiology, LMM, Multi-modality, vision, language and vision applications, classification

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

1. Namguk Kim, PhD - University of Ulsan College of Medicine, Republic of Korea
2. Soon Ho Yoon, MD, PhD - Seoul National University Hospital, Republic of Korea
3. Bold Bayarbaatar, MD, MSc - Intermed Hospital, Ulaanbaatar, Mongolia
4. Boiter, Eric, MS - National Institutes of Health / National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Diseases, USA
5. Hyun-Jin Bae, Ph.D - Promedius inc.
6. Sei Won Lee, MD, PhD - Asan Medical Center, Republic of Korea
7. Young Ae Kang, MD, PhD - Severance Hospital, Republic of Korea
8. The Korean Society of Thoracic Radiology

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Namguk Kim, PhD - University of Ulsan College of Medicine, Republic of Korea

Email: namkugkim@gmail.com

Phone: +822-3010-6573 / Mobile : +8210-3017-4282

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI 2025

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

<https://www.kaggle.com/>

or other platform (<https://grand-challenge.org/>, Naver T2 cloud, etc)

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

<https://www.kaggle.com/competitions/TREAT-MMTB> (we will create it if this proposal is accepted)

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

Publicly available data is allowed

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

The first, second, and third team will receive awards. The awards stipend is to be determined.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

Top three performing methods will be announced publicly on the challenge website. The participants will be invited to present their method during an oral presentation. These teams will be listed as co-authors in the final manuscript.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

Contributors to the submissions covered in the manuscript will be invited to serve as co-authors of the TREAT-MMTB Journal article.

This will include, at a minimum, the top-performing teams selected to present their methodologies at the workshop. Additionally, submissions that exhibit notable scientific value may also be included as co-authors in the journal publication.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

- Participants must submit their models as Docker containers, adhering to the requirements outlined by the Kaggle platform. Each team is permitted to submit one model per task type, such as segmentation or multimodal analysis. The Docker container should encompass all necessary components for execution, including preprocessing, inference, and postprocessing.
- While fine-tuning or training the entire model on the platform will not be permitted, participants are encouraged to leverage pretrained models and ensure the containerized submissions are capable of performing the intended tasks without user interaction. Resource limitations such as computational time and hardware requirements will be predefined to ensure computational feasibility and fairness. These constraints will be clearly communicated prior to the challenge.
- The detailed instructions for container preparation and submission will be provided on the official TREAT-MMTB challenge page hosted on the Kaggle platform. Additionally, participants are required to make the code for their postprocessing steps publicly available after the challenge to foster transparency and reproducibility.
- Evaluation will be performed on a sequestered test set, with only one submission allowed per team during the final phase. The evaluation platform will execute the Docker containers in a fully automated manner, and results will be reported back to participants through the platform interface.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

1. Internal Validation:

Participants will have access to an internal validation set to evaluate the performance of their models. The ground truth for this validation set will not be provided. Teams will be allowed to submit their Docker containers to the

challenge platform once per week during this phase. The evaluation will be executed automatically, and the results will be displayed on a live leaderboard to help teams track their progress. This phase is designed to enable participants to fine-tune their models and ensure proper functionality without compromising the integrity of the ground truth data.

2. External Testing:

Once the final submission deadline has passed, participants' last submitted models will be evaluated on a sequestered external test set.

The external test set results will serve as the sole basis for final rankings, and no additional submissions will be permitted after the final phase begins.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

15 April 2025: Registration opens

Participants will be able to register for the challenge in the Kaggle, from the date of its potential acceptance (April 15, 2025) until the (July 31, 2025).

15 April 2025: Training and validation data release

Availability of training data (with ground truth labels) and validation data (without ground truth labels).

15 August 2025: Docker submission deadline.

Evaluation on testing data by the organizers, only for participants with submitted short papers. Submissions will be scored based on the evaluation metrics, and rankings will be determined accordingly.

22 August 2025: Invitation to participate

Inviting all participants with valid submissions (paper + docker) to present at the conference (type of presentation will be determined within the next 2 weeks)

1 September 2025: Release of Challenge Results

Final challenge results will be announced.

Contacting top-performing teams for preparing oral presentations.

23 September 2025: Challenge at MICCAI

Oral presentation of final top 3 ranked teams and awards ceremony

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

This is being done under a TB portal data use agreement (DUA) with NIAID.

DUA: <https://tbportals.niaid.nih.gov/pdf/TB-Portals-Data-Use-Agreement.pdf>

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

We will provide the evaluation code to challenge participants alongside the final batch of the training data. This release is planned for mid-July.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Participants are required to encapsulate their inference algorithms and associated model weights into a Docker container. The challenge organizers will ensure that the participants' source code and model weights remain confidential and will not be disclosed publicly during the evaluation phase. After the challenge is finished, code and model weights from selected participating teams with leading scores will be made publicly available.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

The TREAT-MMTB challenge is supported by the National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Diseases (NIAID), USA and RIGHT foundation, korea.

Financial support from Promedius inc., etc.

Financial support from The Korean Society of Thoracic Radiology

The industrial sponsors of the challenge will not have access to the test data for the duration of the challenge but may access the data once the full dataset is released to the public upon completion of the challenge.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

CAD,Diagnosis

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Classification

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target cohort for this challenge comprises patients presenting with symptoms suggestive of pulmonary tuberculosis (TB) as well as individuals with normal chest X-rays (CXRs). These groups reflect the diverse population encountered in clinical settings, encompassing both diseased and healthy individuals to ensure the AI model's applicability across a broad diagnostic spectrum. Patients with suspected TB are characterized by the availability of clinical data collected during routine diagnostic workups, including frontal CXRs, sputum sample results (if indicated), and demographic information. CXRs are used to assess radiological features indicative of TB, employing validated scoring systems such as the Timika score. Sputum samples, when obtained, provide information about bacterial burden through microscopy or culture tests. Normal CXRs in this cohort serve as controls, representing patients who do not exhibit radiological or clinical evidence of TB. Including normal CXRs ensures the model's ability to differentiate between healthy individuals and those with pathological findings, thereby improving its robustness and diagnostic utility. This diverse cohort mirrors the population commonly encountered in initial diagnostic settings, ensuring the AI model's applicability in real-world clinical workflows. By integrating normal and TB-affected CXRs, the challenge aims to develop AI tools capable of supporting accurate and reproducible diagnostic and treatment strategies.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge cohort includes datasets curated for training, validation, and testing of AI models focused on pulmonary tuberculosis (TB), as well as normal chest X-rays (CXRs) for comparison. The training and validation datasets are derived from the publicly available National Institute of Allergy and Infectious Diseases (NIAID) TB portal, which compiles data from 13 countries, including annotated CXRs of TB patients and associated metadata such as bacterial burden and cavitation status. For normal CXRs, a separate public dataset is currently under development. This dataset will include annotated normal CXRs and serve as a control group, enabling the AI model to distinguish between healthy and TB-affected individuals. For testing, independent datasets from hospitals in Korea, Mongolia, and Peru are utilized. These datasets consist of locally annotated CXRs (both TB and normal cases) and matched clinical and sputum data, reflecting diverse geographic and clinical contexts. Including normal CXRs in the testing phase ensures that the model can effectively differentiate between healthy and diseased individuals, improving its robustness and generalizability. This approach ensures that the challenge cohort represents real-world diagnostic scenarios, enabling robust evaluation of AI model performance across different populations, healthcare settings, and radiological conditions.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Chest x-ray - poasteroanterior(PA) view

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

Lesion classification for each lobe (cavity, nodule...), Overall percent of abnormal volume, Timika score

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

Epidemiology: age, gender

Clinical information: diagnosis code, bmi

Sputum: Culture, Drug-resistance

Treatment: regimen, duration, outcome

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

thorax shown in chest x-ray data

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

lung in the thorax

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy,Robustness

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

The data was acquired from over 16 countries worldwide, ensuring a diverse representation of clinical settings. Consequently, a variety of imaging devices from multiple manufacturers were used, including but not limited to GE Healthcare, Canon Inc., Fujifilm Holdings Corporation, Siemens AG, and Philips Healthcare.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

Each center utilized its own imaging protocols and equipment configurations, leading to variations in device settings and performance. This diversity enhances the robustness of the dataset by encompassing a wide range of imaging quality and characteristics.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Scientific Research Institute of Lung Diseases, Ministry of Health, Baku (Azerbaijan)
 The United Institute of Informatics Problems, National Academy of Sciences of Belarus, Minsk (Belarus)
 Republican Research and Practical Centre for Pulmonology and Tuberculosis, Minsk (Belarus)
 Shenzhen Center for Chronic Disease Control, Shenzhen (China)
 Fondation Congolaise pour la Recherche Medicale (Republic of the Congo)
 National Center for Tuberculosis and Lung Diseases, Ministry of Health, Tbilisi (Georgia)
 Manipal Academy of Higher Education, Karnataka (India)
 National Science Center of Phthisiopulmonology, Almaty (Kazakhstan)
 National Tuberculosis Center, Bishkek (Kyrgyzstan)
 University Clinical Research Center, Bamako (Mali)
 Universidad Autónoma de Nuevo León, Monterrey (Mexico)
 Phthisiopneumology Institute, Chisinau (Moldova)
 University of Ibadan, Ibadan (Nigeria)
 Marius Nasta Pneumophtisiology Institute, Bucuresti (Romania)
 Hospital Center University De Fann, Senegal (Senegal)
 Perinatal HIV Research Unit, Johannesburg (South Africa)
 Kharkiv National Medical University, Kharkiv (Ukraine)
 National Lung Hospital, Hanoi (Vietnam)
 Asan Medical Center, Seoul (Republic of Korea)
 Seoul National University Hospital, Seoul (Republic of Korea)
 Severance Hospital, Seoul (Republic of Korea)
 Hospital Nacional Dos de Mayo, (Republic of Peru)

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

The diagnosis and treatment decisions for TB patients involved respiratory physicians and other clinical specialists. The labeling of chest X-rays was carried out by radiologists as well as trained general practitioners (GPs) who received specific training for this task. This collaborative approach ensured that the dataset reflects a variety of expertise levels in clinical and radiological assessments.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

Each case in this challenge consists of a comprehensive dataset for a patient presenting with symptoms suggestive of pulmonary tuberculosis (TB) at an outpatient clinic, as well as normal chest X-ray (CXR) cases for comparison. The dataset includes epidemiological information such as the patient's age and gender to provide demographic context. Clinical details include the patient's reported symptoms and body mass index (BMI), offering insights into their overall health and nutritional status. For TB cases, sputum analysis data, including culture results and drug-resistance profiles (if applicable), are also included to reflect the diagnostic process. Radiological data, primarily in the form of chest X-ray (CXR) images, are integral components of the case. This multimodal dataset ensures a thorough representation of each patient's diagnostic journey, supporting the development and evaluation of AI models tailored to real-world clinical scenarios. The dataset will also be designed to offer the necessary diversity in clinical context for both TB and normal CXR cases.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

1. Public data for training and tuning: 2000 TB cases from TB portal, 2000 normal cases from different public data.
2. Internal validation data: 500 TB cases from TB portal, 500 normal cases from different public data.
3. External validation data: total 2680 cases
 - 100 cases from Asan Medical Center, Seoul (Republic of Korea)
 - 100 cases from Seoul National University Hospital, Seoul (Republic of Korea)
 - 100 cases from Severance Hospital, Seoul (Republic of Korea)
 - 100 cases from Intermed Hospital, Ulaanbaatar (Mongolia)
 - 2280 cases from Hospital Nacional Dos de Mayo, (Republic of Peru)

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The selection of specific proportions for training, validation, and test cases in the tuberculosis (TB) challenge was carefully designed to ensure robustness and fairness in model evaluation.

For the training and validation datasets, TB data will be sourced from the TB Portal, while normal data will be obtained from other public datasets currently under construction. To maintain balance, TB data will be sampled to match the number of normal cases. These datasets provide high-quality annotations and metadata, which are essential for developing reliable models. To promote inclusivity and transparency, all available data were shared with participants, ensuring equal access to resources for model development. Twenty percent (20%) of the combined dataset will be reserved for validation purposes, ensuring an unbiased assessment of model performance, as the validation data is not used in training.

For the Republic of Korea, the test set will maintain a 1:1 ratio of TB to normal cases. However, in datasets from other countries, class imbalances will be preserved to reflect the clinical realities of those regions, where TB cases are more prevalent. This approach ensures that the test set mirrors real-world scenarios and challenges, enabling robust assessment of models under varying conditions.

Overall, this design ensures that model performance is rigorously and fairly assessed, reflecting both the diversity and the practical realities of clinical deployment.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

The training, validation, and test cases are designed to reflect real-world challenges encountered in diverse clinical settings.

For the test set, each country's dataset exhibits unique characteristics, including significant class imbalances and differences in image quality or acquisition protocols. For instance, the Republic of Korea dataset maintains a balanced 1:1 ratio of TB to normal cases, whereas datasets from other countries reflect class imbalances aligned

with their local epidemiology. These disparities test the models' ability to generalize across varied clinical scenarios, emphasizing the importance of overcoming real-world challenges such as class imbalance and regional variability.

For the training and validation datasets, TB and normal cases are sourced from different datasets (TB Portal and another public dataset, respectively), which introduces a domain gap. This setup highlights the importance of addressing domain adaptation during model training, as effective adaptation is crucial for developing robust AI solutions capable of handling diverse data sources and real-world variability. By maintaining these characteristics, the challenge aims to evaluate how well models can navigate the complexities of real-world scenarios, including domain shifts and imbalances. This approach underscores the primary goal of the challenge: to develop AI models that are not only accurate but also practical and generalizable, supporting clinicians across diverse clinical contexts and regions.

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

In addition to chest X-ray (CXR) images, the dataset will include radiologist-generated reports. Epidemiological and clinical data will cover patient demographics, TB test results, and relevant clinical information. This multimodal dataset is designed to provide participants with a comprehensive view of the diagnostic and clinical context, enabling the development of AI models that reflect real-world clinical applications and scenarios.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

The training and validation datasets will be sourced from public data available in the TB Portal. These datasets consist of cases that have already been diagnosed as TB, with labels indicating the presence or absence of the disease based on established clinical guidelines. For normal cases, data will be sourced from a separate public dataset, currently under development. Radiologists will review both the radiological reports and images from this dataset to confirm that these cases are normal. This process ensures that the labels for both TB and normal data are accurate, standardized, and consistent with clinical practices.

The reference annotations for classification will involve a thorough validation process. An experienced thoracic radiologist with 18 years of expertise (S.H.Y.) will provide initial reference guidelines for defining TB-positive and normal cases. Radiologists from each participating center will review and validate the labels collaboratively to reach a consensus, ensuring consistency and reliability across the entire dataset.

Two radiologists from each center will complete the labeling by mid-March, and the annotations will be reviewed before the start of the challenge.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

For the test set, the included patients are accurately labeled as either TB or normal based on chest X-rays (CXRs) using clinical standards established at each participating center. This approach ensures that the test set reflects real-world diagnostic practices while maintaining high accuracy and consistency in the classification of TB and normal cases. Detailed protocols for labeling and review processes will be provided to annotators to ensure

standardized and reliable classification across all centers.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The training and validation annotations were performed by radiologists and general practitioners (GPs) under the guidelines provided by the TB Portal. For the test set, annotations will be conducted by two radiologists at each center, following a reference developed by an experienced thoracic radiologist with 18 years of expertise (S.H.Y.).

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

N/A

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The training and validation datasets provided through the NIAID TB portal will include DICOM header information, which will be openly accessible to participants. To ensure standardization, chest X-ray images from multiple hospitals will be preprocessed to conform to a consistent format.

Regarding radiology reports, variations in language and structure exist across different hospitals. To address this, reports will be provided in two clearly defined sections: Findings and Conclusions. However, no additional structured preprocessing will be performed beyond this classification. All reports will be preprocessed into English before being shared with participants.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

1. Inter-annotator Variability: Differences in expertise and interpretation among annotators (e.g., radiologists and GPs for training and validation, or the two radiologists per center for the test set) could lead to inconsistencies in determining TB status from CXRs. Collaborative reviews and adherence to clinical guidelines mitigate these discrepancies, but minor differences in interpretation may still occur.

2. Intra-annotator Variability: Even experienced annotators may show slight inconsistencies in repeated annotations, especially when identifying subtle radiological features indicative of TB.

3. Diagnostic Challenges: Variability may arise in interpreting CXRs due to image quality, patient positioning, or overlapping anatomical structures, which could affect the accuracy of TB diagnosis.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

1. Image Quality Variability: Differences in the quality of the chest X-rays (e.g., resolution, exposure levels, or artifacts) could impact the clarity of radiological features, leading to inconsistent interpretations or annotations for TB classification.

2. Equipment and Acquisition Differences: Variability in imaging equipment and protocols across institutions could result in differences in image characteristics, such as contrast or sharpness, potentially influencing the accuracy of TB classification.

3. **Domain Shift Within Training Data:** The training data includes TB cases from the TB Portal and normal cases sourced from a different public dataset. Difference in imaging protocols, demographic distribution or annotation standards between these datasets could introduce domain shifts that impact model performance.
4. **Domain Shift Between Training and Test Data:** The training and validation data may exhibit different characteristics compared to the test data sourced from various institutions, which could affect the generalizability of models trained on these datasets.
5. **Clinical Context Limitations:** Annotators relying solely on imaging data without access to the full clinical context (e.g., patient symptoms or laboratory findings) may misinterpret certain features, potentially leading to errors in distinguishing TB from normal cases or other abnormalities.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

F1 score

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

Given the significant class imbalance in the test set, the F1-score was chosen as the sole evaluation metric. The F1-score, which is the harmonic mean of precision and recall, effectively balances the trade-off between false positives and false negatives—an essential consideration in biomedical applications such as TB detection where both types of errors can have serious clinical implications.

The test set comprises data from three countries: the Republic of Korea, Mongolia, and Peru. While the dataset from the Republic of Korea is balanced with a 1:1 ratio of TB to normal cases, the data from Mongolia—and especially from Peru, where the ratio can be as high as 10:1 in favor of TB cases—exhibits marked class imbalance. By computing the F1-score over all patient data combined, the evaluation metric provides a single, comprehensive measure of the model's overall performance, ensuring that it reflects the ability to generalize across diverse populations and varied class distributions.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

To rank the submitted algorithms, we first aggregate all predictions across the entire test set and compute a single overall F1-score for each algorithm. This overall score captures the model's ability to balance false positives and false negatives across all cases from the three countries.

If two algorithms achieve the same overall F1-score, the tie is resolved by comparing their performance on a per-country basis. Specifically, we calculate the F1-score for each country separately and then identify the lowest F1-score for each algorithm. The algorithm with the higher minimum country-specific F1-score is ranked higher, as

this indicates more consistent performance across all populations.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

For any submission with missing predictions on certain test cases, those cases are treated as misclassifications when computing the overall F1-score. In other words, each missing result is considered an error—either as a false negative or a false positive, depending on the ground truth—thereby penalizing the submission. This approach ensures that every test case contributes to the final performance metric and discourages incomplete submissions. By incorporating the penalty for missing results into the aggregated global confusion matrix, the overall F1-score naturally decreases for algorithms with incomplete outputs, leading to a lower ranking in the final evaluation.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

The ranking scheme was designed to ensure that the evaluation metric reflects both overall performance and consistency across diverse patient populations, which is crucial in biomedical applications like TB detection. Given the significant class imbalance, the overall F1-score is used because it effectively balances the trade-off between false positives and false negatives. This single, aggregated metric provides a comprehensive measure of how well an algorithm performs across all cases.

In addition, when two algorithms achieve the same overall F1-score, the tie is resolved by comparing their performance on a per-country basis. Specifically, the algorithm with the higher minimum country-specific F1-score is ranked higher. This tie-breaker ensures that the selected model not only performs well overall but also maintains robust and consistent performance across different cohorts, which is essential when the clinical implications of misclassifications can vary by population.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

Statistical significance will be evaluated by analyzing between-class variability across selected subsets, such as case difficulty and participant demographics. This approach will provide insights into how robust the methods are under varying conditions. Python will be used to conduct all statistical analyses, including ranking calculations and variability assessments.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

The described statistical methods were chosen to provide a robust and fair evaluation of the submitted algorithms. By assessing between-class variability across subsets such as case difficulty and demographics, we aim to ensure that the models perform consistently across different scenarios. This approach also accounts for potential domain shifts, reflecting real-world variations.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

1. **Combining Algorithms via Ensembling:** After individual evaluations, ensemble methods (e.g., averaging predictions or majority voting) may be explored to assess whether combining multiple submissions improves performance.
2. **Inter-Algorithm Variability:** Variability in performance across algorithms will be analyzed by comparing their scores on specific subsets of test cases (e.g., cases with mild, moderate, or severe TB). This analysis will identify strengths and weaknesses of different methods and highlight scenarios where certain algorithms excel or struggle.
3. **Common Problems/Biases of Submitted Methods:** A review of errors across submissions will be conducted to identify common biases, such as systematic under-segmentation in cavity detection or misclassification of severe TB cases. These insights could guide future algorithm development and highlight areas where additional data or refinement is needed.

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

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Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

N/A